

AN INTRODUCTION TO TIKZ

Dr. N.K. Sudev

Department of Mathematics,
CHRIST (Deemed to be University),
Bangalore-560029, India.

05-07, November 2018

1 Setting Up the Environment

1.1 Necessary Codes in the Preamble

In the beginning, follow the usual steps as given below:

1. Define document class - *article* or *standalone* (the class for individual examples). (Use `\documentclass{article}` or `\documentclass{standalone}`).
2. Introduce the packages such as *graphicx*, *caption* and *subcaption*. This can be done by writing the command `\usepackage{graphicx,caption,subcaption}` in the preamble.
3. Include the Tikz package to the document by writing `\usepackage{tikz}` in the preamble.
4. Now we can include different tikz libraries according to our requirements.

Some of the very useful Tikz libraries are:

1. *arrows* - to create and customise arrows.
2. *automata* - to draw finite state automata and Turing Machines.
3. *backgrounds* - to define backgrounds of pictures.
4. *calc* - to make complex coordinate calculations.
5. *calendar* - to display calendars.
6. *er* (entry relation) - to define nodes and edges between nodes with their attributes.
7. *mindmap* - to draw the main focus point, in the middle, with sub-points branching off.
8. *folding* - useful for producing real calendars.

9. *patterns*- defines patterns for filling areas.
10. *plotthandlers, plotmarks* - to draw nodes and curves in different styles.
11. *shapes* - uses to define shapes (other than rectangle, circle and co-ordinate).
12. *snake* - to create curved lines.
13. *topaths* - to draw paths between nodes.
14. *trees*- draws tree diagrams.
15. *plotthandlers, plotmarks* - to draw nodes and curves
16. *positioning* - to adjust positions of nodes and their coordinates and to create gridlines as in the graph sheets.
17. *decorations.markings* - for advanced customisations of figures and shapes

we can include the libraries using the command

```
\usetikzlibrary{
  intersections, arrows.meta,
  automata,er,calc,
  backgrounds,
  mindmap,folding,
  patterns,
  decorations.markings,
  fit,snakes,
  shapes,matrix,
  positioning,
  shapes.geometric,
  arrows,through
}
```

1.2 Figure Environments

To draw a figure, we use the following tikz environment:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
  Write your Tikz Code here...!!!
\end{tikzpicture}
```

To draw a figure with caption, we use the following tikz environment:

```
\begin{figure}[placement]
\centering
\begin{tikzpicture}
Write your Tikz Code here...!!!
\end{tikzpicture}
\end{figure}
```

To draw a figure with caption, we use the following tikz environment:

```

\begin{figure}[placement]
\centering
\begin{subfigure}[b]{0.45\textwidth}
\begin{tikzpicture}
Write your Tikz Code for the first figure here...!!!
\end{tikzpicture}
\caption{Subcaption for the first subfigure}
\end{subfigure}
\quad
\begin{subfigure}[b]{0.45\textwidth}
\begin{tikzpicture}
Write your Tikz Code for the second figure here...!!!
\end{tikzpicture}
\caption{Subcaption for the second subfigure}
\end{subfigure}
\caption{Your figure caption here}
\end{figure}

```

2 Drawing and Decorating Lines

1. To draw a line between, we can use the code:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) --(5,0);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

This will give us the output

2. The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) --(5,0) -- (2.5,2.5);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

gives us following output:

3. The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) --(5,0) -- (2.5,2.5) -- (0,0);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

gives us following output:

4. Scaling of the figures can be done as follows:

(a) The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[xscale=2]
\draw (0,0) --(5,0) -- (2.5,2.5) -- (0,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us following output:

(b) The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[yscale=1.5]
\draw (0,0) --(5,0) -- (2.5,2.5) -- (0,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us following output:

(c) The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=0.5]
\draw (0,0) --(5,0) -- (2.5,2.5) -- (0,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us following output:

5. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[yscale=1.5]
\draw [->] (0,0) --(5,0);
\draw [<-] (5,1) -- (2.5,2.5);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us following output:

6. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [<->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (3,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

will create the figure

7. The thickness of the lines can be adjusted using the code:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [ultra thick] (0,1) -- (2,1);
\draw [thick] (0,0.5) -- (2,0.5);
\draw [thin] (0,0) -- (2,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

and the output will be as follows:

8. The option “help lines” is made specially to be fine gray lines for showing special points as shown below:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [<->,thick] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw [dashed] (0,1.5) -- (3,0);
\draw [dotted] (0,0) -- (2,2);
\draw [help lines] (1,0) -- (1,1) -- (0,1);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

which yields the following diagram:

9. We can also decide line width using custom commands as follows

The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [line width=12] (0,0) -- (2,0);
\draw [line width=0.1cm] (0,1) -- (2,1);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

yields the following output:

10. We can also color the lines by using the code:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [yellow] (0,2.5) -- (4,2.5);
\draw [cyan] (0, 2) -- (4,2);
\draw [purple] (0,1.5) -- (4,1.5);
\draw [green] (0,1) -- (4,1);
\draw [red] (0, 0.5) -- (4,0.5);
\draw [blue] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

and the output will be as follows:

Note: We have the following default colors: red .

In addition to these one can define new colors according to their preferences using the command `\definecolor{myblue}{rgb}{24,40,120}`

Here, the colour strips are created using the command

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [red, line width=6] (0,0) -- (.5,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

3 Drawing Curves

1. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [blue] (0,0) rectangle (3,2);
\draw [red, ultra thick] (6,1) circle [radius=1];;
\draw [violet] (10,1) arc [radius=2,start angle=45,end angle= 120];
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives the output

2. We can make paths take smoother turns:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [<->, rounded corners, thick, purple] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (3,0);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

which gives you

3. We can do curves without plotting all the points. See an easy one:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[very thick] (0,0) to [out=90,in=195] (2,1.5);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

which yields

4. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [<->,thick, cyan] (0,0) to [out=90,in=180] (1,1)
to [out=0,in=180] (2,0) to [out=0,in=180] (3,1) to [out=0,in=-180] (4,1) ;
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives the output

5. Tikz also has a math engine which enables you to plot functions:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[xscale=2,yscale=2]
\draw [<->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\draw[green, ultra thick, domain=0:1] plot (\x, {\x*\x*\x+\x-0.025});
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives you

Many mathematical functions are available in default. Some of them are:

```

factorial(\x),
sqrt(\x),
pow(\x,y),
exp(\x),
ln(\x),
log10(\x),
log2(\x),
abs(\x),
mod(\x,y) - (x modulo y),
round(\x) - (rounds x to the nearest integer),
floor(\x),
ceil(\x),
sin(\x) - (sinx in degrees),
sin(\x r) - (sinx in radians),
cos(\x),
cos(\x,r),
tan(\x),
tan(\x,r),
min(\x,y,),
max(\x,y) etc.

```

6. The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [help lines, ->] (0,0) -- (8,0);
\draw [help lines, ->] (0,-1.1) -- (0,1.1);
\draw [green,domain=0:2*pi] plot (\x, {2*(sin(\x r)* ln(\x+1))/2});
\draw [red,domain=0:pi] plot (\x, {2*sin(\x r)});
\draw [blue, domain=pi:2*pi] plot (\x, {2*cos(\x r)*exp(\x/exp(2*pi))});
\end{tikzpicture}

```

will give us the following diagram.

4 Filling up Shapes

We can fill figures and shapes with colours. See the following illustrations.

The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [fill=red,ultra thick] (0,0) rectangle (1,1);
\draw [fill=red,ultra thick,red] (2,0) rectangle (3,1);
\draw [blue, fill=blue] (4,0) -- (5,1) -- (4.75,0.15) -- (4,0);
\draw [fill] (7,0.5) circle [radius=0.1];
\draw [fill=orange] (9,0) rectangle (11,1);
\draw [fill=white] (9.25,0.25) rectangle (10,1.5);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

gives the result:

We can define new colours according to our preference as mentioned earlier.

5 Putting Labels

In almost all figures we have to assign labels to the parts of the figure (marking angles, lengths etc.). (Here we have to use the library *positioning* for better placement of labels). To write labels at certain positions, we need to create nodes using `\node` command.

For example, the code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}

```

gives us the output

Note that the node is invisible until we define a shape for the node. We shall define shapes for nodes using `\node[shape]` command. For this we need to define the characters of the curves in the shape concerned using the `\tikzstyle{text} = {definition}` environment. We may have to include the libraries *shapes*, *snakes*, *matrix* etc. according to the requirements.

For example, the code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,circle] at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,circle] at (1,1) [label={yes}] {};
\end{tikzpicture}
```


The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,circle,fill] at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}
```


The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[xscale=3,yscale=3]
\draw [thick, <->] (0,1) -- (0,0) -- (1,0);
\node [below right] at (1,0) {$x$};
\node [left] at (0,1) {$y$};
\draw[fill] (.4,.6) circle [radius=.5pt];
\node[above right] at (.4,.6) {$A$};
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives the output

The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,circle,fill=blue] at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,rectangle,fill=green] at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw [thick, <->] (0,2) -- (0,0) -- (2,0);
\node[draw,diamond,fill=red!50] at (1,1) {yes};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


5.1 Node Shapes & Matrix Environment

The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=2]
\tikzstyle{ann} = [draw=none,fill=none,right]
\matrix[nodes={draw, ultra thick, fill=blue!20},
row sep=0.3cm,column sep=0.5cm] {
\node[draw=none,fill=none] {Plain node}; &
\node[rectangle] {Rectangle}; &
\node[circle] {Circle};\backslash

```

```

\node[ellipse] {Ellipse};&
\node[circle split] {Circle \nodepart{lower} split};&
\node[forbidden sign,text width=4em, text centered]
{Forbidden sign};\\
\node[diamond] {Diamond};&
\node[cross out] {Cross out};&
\node[strike out] {Strike out};\\
\node[regular polygon,regular polygon sides=5] {$n=5$};&
\node[regular polygon,regular polygon sides=7] {$n=7$};&
\node[regular polygon,regular polygon sides=9] {$n=9$};&
\node[ann]{Regular polygon};\\
\node[star,star points=4] {$p=4$};&
\node[star,star points=7,star point ratio=0.8] {$p=7$};&
\node[star,star points=10] {$p=9$};&
\node[ann]{Star};\\
};
\end{tikzpicture}

```

gives us the result as follows:
the code

6 LaTeX Graphics using TikZ

1. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) -- (4,0) -- (4,4) -- (0,4) -- cycle;
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us

2. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) parabola (3,3);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

gives us

3. To draw a curved line we use *control points*. We begin with our starting co-ordinate, then use two dots followed by the keyword *controls* and then the co-ordinates of our control points separated by an *and*.

For example, consider the command `\draw (0,0) .. controls (0,4) and (4,0) .. (4,4);` and the output will be as follows:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (0,0) .. controls (0,4) and (4,0) .. (4,4);
\end{tikzpicture}
```


4. The code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}  
\draw (0,0) .. controls (0,4) and (4,0) .. (4,4) .. controls (5,5)  
and (6,2) .. (6,6);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```


5. By the code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}  
\draw (2,2) circle (2cm);  
\draw (9,2) ellipse (2cm and 1.5cm);  
\draw (15,1.5) arc (0:75:3cm);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```


6. The code `\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-3,-3) grid (8,8);` wil give you the grid lines as follows:

7. Consider the code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}  
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```

the output will be:

8. We can fill areas in the above figure by adding the commands like
`\fill[blue!40!white] (0,0) rectangle (4,4);` (see the output below).

That is, the code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}  
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);  
\fill[blue!40!white] (-1,-1) rectangle (4.5,4.5);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```

will give the output as follows:

9. We can add boarder also using the `\filldraw` command. For example, the command

That is, the code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\filldraw[fill=blue!40!white, draw=black] (0,0) rectangle (4,4);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

will yield the figure

10. We can draw different shapes exactly as in a graph sheet and assign colours to these shapes. For example, the code

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\draw [fill=brown!50] (-1,-1) -- (0,1) -- (2,3) -- (0,4) -- cycle;
\draw [fill=green!40] (2,2) -- (4,4) -- (6,5) --(4,6) -- cycle;
\end{tikzpicture}
```

will give us the following output:

11. Instead of assigning a single colour, we can assign some colour gradients also to the shapes using the `\shade` command. As an illustration, consider the following command:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=0.75]
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\shade[left color=blue,right color=red] (-1,-1) rectangle (6,6);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the output

12. Consider the following command:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=0.75]
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\shade[top color=blue,bottom color=yellow] (-1,-1) rectangle (6,6);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the output

13. Consider the following command:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=0.75]
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\shade[inner color=green,outer color=red] (-1,-1) rectangle (6,6);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the output

14. As explained above, we can insert the borders using `\shadeddraw` command. See the example:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\shadeddraw[inner color=blue,outer color=red, draw=black] (0,0)
```

```
rectangle (4,4);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the output

15. The `shade` can replace `\filldraw` and the output will be as follows.

```
\begin{tikzpicture}  
\shade[shading=ball, ball color=blue] (0,0) circle (2);  
\shade[shading=ball, ball color=white] (5,0) circle (2);  
\shade[shading=ball, ball color=black] (10,0) circle (2);  
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the output

7 Coordinate System

16. The coordinate axes can be drawn as follows:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}%[scale=0.75]
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\draw[thick,->] (-2,0) -- (6.5,0);
\draw[thick,->] (0,-2) -- (0,6.5);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the figure as

17. Numbers/units can be marked on the coordinate axes as follows:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}%[scale=0.75]
\draw[thick,->] (-2,0) -- (6.5,0);
\draw[thick,->] (0,-2) -- (0,6.5);
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.9,-2.9) grid (6.9,6.9);
\foreach \x in {-2,-1,0,1,2,3,4,5}
\draw (\x cm,1pt) -- (\x cm,-1pt) node[anchor=north] {$\x$};
\foreach \y in {-2,-1,0,1,2,3,4,5}
\draw (1pt,\y cm) -- (-1pt,\y cm) node[anchor=west] {$\y$};
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the figure as

18. Graphs can also be plotted in the above grid environment as explained below:

```
\draw[step=1cm,gray,very thin] (-2.5,-2.5) grid (6.9,6.9);
\draw[thick,->] (-2,0) -- (6.5,0);
\draw[thick,->] (0,-2) -- (0,6.5);
\foreach \x in {-2,-1,0,1,2,3,4,5}
\draw (\x cm,1pt) -- (\x cm,-1pt) node[anchor=north] {$\x$};
\foreach \y in {-2,-1,0,1,2,3,4,5}
\draw (1pt,\y cm) -- (-1pt,\y cm) node[anchor=west] {$\y$};
\draw [thick,->] (0,0) -- (1,4) -- (2,2)-- (3,2) -- (4,1) -- (5,3);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

yields the figure as

8 Flow Charts

To create the shapes, we use in flowcharts, the libraries `shapes.geometric` and `arrows`. Just add these libraries in the preamble.

To begin with, we need to define the required shapes using

```
\tikzstyle{shape-name}=[attribute1,attribute2,...]:
```

1. The start & stop buttons can be defined as follows:

```
\tikzstyle {ss} = [rectangle, rounded corners, minimum width=3cm,
minimum height=1cm,text centered, draw=black, fill=red!30]
```

Now, the command `\node (start) [ss] {Start};` gives us the output

2. The input-output boxes can be defined as follows:

```
\tikzstyle{io}=[trapezium, trapezium left angle=70, trapezium right angle=110, minimum width=3cm, minimum height=1cm, text centered, draw=black, fill=blue!30]
```

3. Now the process boxes and decision boxes can be created as follows:

```
\tikzstyle{proc}=[rectangle, minimum width=3cm, minimum height=1cm, text centered, draw=black, fill=orange!30]
```

and

```
\tikzstyle{dec} = [diamond, minimum width=3cm, minimum height=1cm, text centered, draw=black, fill=green!30]
```

4. Now, it remains to define arrows which can be done as follows:

```
\tikzstyle{arrow} = [thick,->,>=stealth]
```

5. Now, the commands

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\node (start) [ss] at (0,14) {Start};
\node (in1) [io] at (0,12) {Input};
\node (pro1) [proc] at (0,10) {Process 1};
\node (dec1) [dec] at (0,7) {Decision 1};
\node (pro2a) [proc] at (0,4) {Process 2a};
\node (pro2b) [proc] at (4,7) {Process 2b};
\node (out1) [io] at (0,2) {Output};
\node (stop) [ss] at (0,0) {Stop};
\end{tikzpicture}
```

give us the following output

6. Now, the commands

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\node (start) [ss] at (0,14) {Start};
\node (in1) [io] at (0,12) {Input};
\node (pro1) [proc] at (0,10) {Process 1};
\node (dec1) [dec] at (0,7) {Decision 1};
\node (pro2a) [proc] at (0,4) {Process 2a};
\node (pro2b) [proc] at (4,7) {Process 2b};
\node (out1) [io] at (0,2) {Output};
\node (stop) [ss] at (0,0) {Stop};
\draw [arrow] (start) -- (in1);
\draw [arrow] (in1) -- (pro1);
\draw [arrow] (pro1) -- (dec1);
\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- (pro2a);
\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- (pro2b);

```

```

%\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- node {yes} (pro2a);
%\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- node {no} (pro2b);
\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- node[anchor=east] {yes} (pro2a);
\draw [arrow] (dec1) -- node[anchor=south] {no} (pro2b);
%\draw [arrow] (pro2b) -- (pro1);
\draw [arrow] (pro2b) |- (pro1);
\draw [arrow] (pro2a) -- (out1);
\draw [arrow] (out1) -- (stop);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

give us the following output

9 More on Shapes

1. Some special types of arrows can be created using the following commands:

```
\draw[->] (0,0) -- (14,0);
\draw[dotted, >->>] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw[|<->|] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw[dashed, o-)] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw[loosely dashed] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw[densely dotted] (0,0) -- (4,0);
\draw[->] (0,0) .. controls (2,-1) .. (4, 0);
```


2. We can also draw figures using the polar coordinates also. For example, consider the command:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[color=red] (0,0) -- (40:1);
\draw[color=blue] (0,0) -- (160:1);
\draw[thick] (0,0) -- (90:1);
\draw[color=green] (40:1) arc (40:160:1);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Here, we get the figure

3. Use of the `intersections` library can be illustrated as follows:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
% Draw to path and give a name to them
\draw [red, name path={red line}] (0,0) -- (4,3);
\draw [blue, name path={blue curve}] (1,-0.5) to[out=80, in=100] (3,2);
% use the intersections on a path to give them coordinates
% and draw a line between them
\draw [green, name intersections={of=red line and blue curve,
by={first intersect, second intersect}}]
(first intersect) -- (second intersect);
% one can use the coordinates further on
\node [above] at (first intersect) {A};
\node [below] at (second intersect) {B};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


4. A path is a series of straight and curved line segments. We can draw paths, fill them colours or can use for clipping of subsequent drawings. After a `\clip` command, all subsequent drawings are clipped, only the parts inside the clipping region are drawn.

For example,

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\path[clip, draw] (1,1)--(2,2)--(3,1)--cycle;
\path[fill=blue!50] (2, 1.7) circle (.8);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the output

5. We can use the *scope* environment to restrict the effect of clipping, as shown in the following example:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw (-2, 1.5) rectangle (2, -1.5);
\begin{scope}
\clip (-0.5, 0) circle (1);
\clip ( 0.5, 0) circle (1);
\fill[color=gray] (-2,1.5)rectangle (2,-1.5);
\end{scope}
\draw (-0.5, 0) circle (1);
\draw ( 0.5, 0) circle (1);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the output

6. We can also create loops (like loops in algorithms/programs), as explained below:

The codes

```

\draw[->] (-5.5,0) -- (5.5,0) node [below] {$\mathbb{R}$};
\foreach \x in {-5,...,5}
\draw (\x, 0.1) -- (\x, -0.1) node [below] {\x};
%
%
\foreach \x in {1,3,...,10}

```

```

\shade[ball color=red!\x 0!green] (\x,0) circle (3mm);
%
%
\foreach \x in {9,...,1}
\draw[fill=blue!\x0] (-0.1*\x - 1, -0.1*\x )
rectangle (0.1*\x + 1, 0.1*\x );

```

respectively give the following diagrams

7. Labeling of lines can be done as given below:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\draw[->,thick] (0,0) -- (4,2) node[pos=.5,sloped,above] {$x$};
\draw[->,thick] (0,0) -- (4,-2) node[pos=.5,sloped,below] {$y$};
\end{tikzpicture}

```


8. Figures including shapes can be drawn as follows:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=2]
\coordinate [label=left:$A$] (A) at (0,0);
\coordinate [label=right:$B$] (B) at (1.25,0.25);
\draw (A) -- (B);
\node (D) [draw,circle through=(B),label=left:$D$] at (A) {};
\node (E) [draw,circle through=(A),label=right:$E$] at (B) {};
\coordinate[label=above:$C$] (C) at (intersection 2 of D and E);

```

```

\draw [red] (A) -- (C);
\draw [red] (B) -- (C);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

generates the diagram (note that the library *through* is to be used here.)

10 Graph Theory Using Tikz

Tikz creates amazingly neat and beautiful and graphs in graph theory. To draw a path, we can use the following Tikz code.

```

\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle,node distance=1.8cm]
\begin{tikzpicture}
\node [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (1) {};
\node [label=below:$c_1$] (2) [right of=1] {};
\node [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (3) [right of=2] {};
\node [label=below:$c_1$] (4) [right of=3] {};
\node [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (5) [right of=4] {};
\node [label=below:$c_1$] (6) [right of=5] {};
\node [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (7) [right of=6] {};
\draw
(1) -- (2)
(2) -- (3)
(3) -- (4)
(4) -- (5)
(5) -- (6)
(6) -- (7);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

and the output will be as follows:

Note that the commands such as [right of=a], [left of=a], [above of=a] and [below of=a] can be used to position shapes in flowcharts also.

The command `node distance=1.8cm` creates a distance 1.8cm between two adjacent nodes.

10.1 Graphs Using Polar Coordinates

1. To draw cycles and/or vertices in a cyclic manner, it is better to use polar coordinates system in Tikz. Look at the following code:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle];
\node (v0) at (0:0) {$v_0$};
\node (v1) at ( 0:2) {$v_1$};
\node (v2) at ( 72:2) {$v_2$};
\node (v3) at (2*72:2) {$v_3$};
\node (v4) at (3*72:2) {$v_4$};
\node (v5) at (4*72:2) {$v_5$};
\draw (v0) -- (v1)
(v0) -- (v2)
(v0) -- (v3)
(v0) -- (v4)
(v0) -- (v5);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

Note that in the command line `\node (v0) at (0:0) {v_0};`, (v0) defines the name of the corresponding vertex. Putting names for vertices is essential for drawing edges between vertices. Now, `at (a:b)` defines the position of that point at an angle a^{deg} from the horizontal and radius b points.

The command `\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle];` defines the attributes of the vertices. Also, while drawing the edges, note that the semi-colon is placed only after the last edge is defined.

Then, the above code will provide us the following output:

2. A cycle on five vertices can be created using the command

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle];
%\node (v0) at (0:0) {$v_0$};
\node (v1) at (0:2) {$v_1$};
\node (v2) at (72:2) {$v_2$};
\node (v3) at (2*72:2) {$v_3$};
\node (v4) at (3*72:2) {$v_4$};
\node (v5) at (4*72:2) {$v_5$};
\draw (v1) -- (v2)
(v2) -- (v3)
(v3) -- (v4)
(v4) -- (v5)
(v1) -- (v5);
\end{tikzpicture}

```


3. Labeling can be done in a different way so that labels appear outside of the nodes. See the example:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle];
\node (v0) at (0:0) [label=below:$v_0$] {};
\node (v1) at ( 0:3) [label=below:$v_1$] {};
\node (v2) at ( 72:3) [label=below:$v_2$] {};
\node (v3) at (2*72:3) [label=below:$v_3$] {};
\node (v4) at (3*72:3) [label=below:$v_4$] {};
\node (v5) at (4*72:3) [label=below:$v_5$] {};
\draw (v0) -- (v1)
(v0) -- (v2)
(v0) -- (v3)
(v0) -- (v4)
(v0) -- (v5);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

which gives the output as

4. Labeling can be done in a different way so that labels appear outside of the nodes. See the example:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\tikzstyle{every node}=[draw,shape=circle];
\node (v0) at (0:0) [fill,label=below:$v_0$] {};
\node (v1) at ( 0:3) [fill,label=below:$v_1$] {};
\node (v2) at ( 72:3) [fill,label=below:$v_2$] {};
\node (v3) at (2*72:3) [fill,label=below:$v_3$] {$v_3$};
\node (v4) at (3*72:3) [fill,label=below:$v_4$] {$v_4$};
\node (v5) at (4*72:3) [fill,label=below:$v_5$] {$v_5$};
\draw (v0) -- (v1)
(v0) -- (v2)
(v0) -- (v3)
(v0) -- (v4)
(v0) -- (v5);
\end{tikzpicture}
```

which gives the output as

We can also customise the vertex attributes with the entire document globally using some commands like `\newcommand{\vertex}{\node[vertex]}` in the preamble. Also, the tikz-style codes can be written in square brackets as shown in the following.

```

\begin{figure}[h!]
\centering
\begin{tikzpicture}[auto,node distance=1.8 cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries}]
\vertex [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (1) {};
\vertex [label=below:$c_1$] (2) [right of=1] {};
\vertex [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (3) [right of=2] {};
\vertex [label=below:$c_1$] (4) [right of=3] {};
\vertex [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (5) [right of=4] {};
\vertex [label=below:$c_1$] (6) [right of=5] {};
\vertex [fill,label=below:$c_2$] (7) [right of=6] {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small}]
(1) edge node {} (2)
(2) edge node {} (3)
(3) edge node {} (4)
(4) edge node {} (5)
(5) edge node {} (6)
(6) edge node {} (7);
\end{tikzpicture}
\caption{The path  $P_7$  with  $\chi^+$  colouring}\label{pathmaxorder}
\end{figure}

```

The output of the above will be as follows:

The code `\path` can be used in place of `\draw` so that labeling and colouring becomes easier.

The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[auto,node distance=1.5 cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries}]
\vertex (v1) at (0:3) [label=right:$c_1$]{$v_1$};
\vertex (v2) at (315:3) [label=below:$c_2$]{$v_2$};
\vertex (v3) at (270:3) [label=below:$c_1$]{$v_3$};
\vertex (v4) at (225:3) [label=below:$c_2$]{$v_4$};
\vertex (v5) at (180:3) [label=left:$c_1$]{$v_5$};
\vertex (v6) at (135:3) [label=above:$c_2$]{$v_6$};
\vertex (v7) at (90:3) [label=above:$c_1$]{$v_7$};
\vertex (v8) at (45:3) [label=above:$c_2$]{$v_8$};
\path
(v1) edge (v2)
(v1) edge (v8)
(v2) edge (v3)
(v3) edge (v4)
(v4) edge (v5)
(v5) edge (v6)
(v6) edge (v7)
(v7) edge (v8);
\end{tikzpicture}

```

creates the cycle

Multiple edges and loops can be created using commands as shown in the following Tikz code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[auto,node distance=2.5cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries}]
\vertex (v1) at (0,0) [fill,label={below:$v_1$}]{};
\vertex (v2) at (3,0) [fill,label={below:$v_2$}]{};
\vertex (v3) at (3,3) [fill,label={above:$v_3$}]{};
\vertex (v4) at (0,3) [fill,label={above:$v_4$}]{};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small},line width=1pt]

```

```

(v1) edge node {$e_1$} (v2)
(v2) edge node {$e_2$}(v3)
(v3) edge node {$e_3$}(v4)
(v4) edge [bend left] node {$e_4$} (v1)
(v4) edge [bend right] node {$e_5$} (v1)
(v4) edge [loop left,looseness=100] node {$e_6$} (v4)
(v2) edge [loop right,looseness=100] node {$e_7$} (v2)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

which gives the following output:

The codes `loop left`, `loop right`, `loop above`, `loop below`, `loop above right` etc. can be used for correct positioning of the loop. The command `looseness=a` decides the shape of the loop.

Graphs with dashed and/or dotted edges can be created using the commands as given below:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\vertex (1) at (0,0) [label={left:$v_1$}] {};
\vertex (2) at (0.75,0.65) [label={above:$v_2$}] {};
\vertex (3) at (0.75,-0.65) [label={below:$v_3$}] {};
\vertex (4) at (1.5,0) [label={left:$v_4$}] {};
\vertex (5) at (2.5,0) [label={right:$v_5$}] {};
\vertex (6) at (3.25,0.65) [label={above:$v_6$}] {};
\vertex (7) at (3.25,-0.65) [label={below:$v_7$}] {};
\vertex (8) at (4,0) [label={right:$v_8$}] {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small},line width=1pt]
(1) edge node {} (2)
(1) edge node {} (3)
(2) edge node {} (3)
(2) edge [dashed] node {} (4)
(3) edge [dashed] node {} (4)
(2) edge [densely dotted] node {} (6)
(3) edge [densely dashed] node {} (7)
(5) edge [dashed] node {} (6)
(5) edge [loosely dotted] node {} (7)
(6) edge [loosely dashed] node {} (7)
(6) edge node {} (8)
(7) edge node {} (8)

```

```

;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

This will yields the figure:

Set-labels can be assigned to the graphs by using the Tikz code given below:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[auto,node distance=1.5cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries}]
%
\node [circle,fill] (u1) at (0:2.25) [label={right:$\emptyset$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u2) at (315:2.25) [label={right:$\{x_1\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u3) at (270:2.25) [label={below:$\{x_1,x_2\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u4) at (225:2.25) [label={left:$\{x_2\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u5) at (180:2.25) [label={left:$\{x_2,x_3\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u6) at (135:2.25) [label={left:$\{x_3\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u7) at (90:2.25) [label={above:$\{x_1,x_3\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u8) at (45:2.25) [label={right:$\{x_4\}$}] {};
\node [circle,fill] (u) at (0:0) [label={above:$\{x_3,x_4\}$}] {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small}]
(u1) edge node {} (u2)
(u2) edge node {} (u3)
edge node {} (u)
(u3) edge node {} (u4)
(u4) edge node {} (u5)
edge node {} (u)
(u5) edge node {} (u6)
(u6) edge node {} (u7)
edge node {} (u)
(u7) edge node {} (u8)
(u8) edge node {} (u1)
edge node {} (u)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

The above code will produce a figure as given below:

In a similar manner, we can assign labels to edges also. For example,

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=1.5,auto,node distance=1.5cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries},el/.style = {inner
every label/.append style = {font=\tiny}]
\vertex [fill] (1) at (0,0) {};
\vertex [fill] (2) at (2,0) {};
\vertex [fill] (3) at (1.5,2.5) {};
\vertex [fill] (4) at (-0.5,1.5) {};
\vertex [fill] (5) at (1,1) {};
\vertex [fill] (6) at (-1,0) {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small},line width=0.5pt]
(1) edge node [el,below] {$e_4$} (2)
(2) edge node [el,above] {$e_3$} (3)
(3) edge node [el,above] {$e_2$} (4)
(4) edge node [el,above] {$e_5$} (1)
(4) edge node [el,above] {$e_1$} (6)
(5) edge node [el,below] {$e_9$} (1)
(5) edge node [el,below] {$e_8$} (2)
(5) edge node [el,below] {$e_7$} (3)
(5) edge node [el,above] {$e_6$} (4)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the figure

Edges can be given set-labels by using the commands as shown in the below Tikz code:

```

\begin{tikzpicture}[scale=1.5,auto,node distance=1.5cm,
thick,main node/.style={circle,draw,font=\sffamily\Large\bfseries},e1/.style = {inner
every label/.append style = {font=\tiny}}
\vertex [fill] (1) at (0,0) {};
\vertex [fill] (2) at (2,0) {};
\vertex [fill] (3) at (1.5,2.5) {};
\vertex [fill] (4) at (-0.5,1.5) {};
\vertex [fill] (5) at (1,1) {};
\vertex [fill] (6) at (-1,0) {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small},line width=0.5pt]
(1) edge node [e1,below] {$\{4\}$} (2)
(2) edge node [e1,above] {$\{1,2\}$} (3)
(3) edge node [e1,above] {$\emptyset$} (4)
(4) edge node [e1,above] {$\{1,2,3\}$} (1)
(4) edge node [e1,above] {$e_1$} (6)
(5) edge node [e1,below] {$e_9$} (1)
(5) edge node [e1,below] {$e_8$} (2)
(5) edge node [e1,below] {$e_7$} (3)
(5) edge node [e1,above] {$e_6$} (4)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

which gives the output

Note that the package *er* is necessary to use `e1`.

11 Directed graphs Using Tikz

When use the command `arrow` or the symbol `->`, normally arrow marks will appear at the end of the edges. Using certain edge decorations, we can decide the position of the arrow mark. For example, see the following code:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}[x=1.3cm, y=1cm, every edge/.style={draw, postaction={decorate,
decoration={markings, mark=at position 0.5 with {\arrow{>}}}}}]
\vertex (1) at (0,0) [fill] {};
\vertex (2) at (2,0) [fill] {};
\vertex (3) at (2,2) [fill] {};
\vertex (4) at (0,2) [fill] {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small}, line width=0.5pt]
(1) edge (2)
(2) edge (3)
(3) edge (4)
(4) edge (1)
(1) edge (3)
(2) edge (4)
;
\end{tikzpicture}
```

The output will be

11.1 vertex and Edge Coloring

We can assign colors to the vertices by giving the attribute `fill=color name` in the attribute square bracket of definition the corresponding vertex. See the following code for example:

```
\begin{tikzpicture}
\vertex [fill=red] (1) at (0,0) {};
\vertex [fill=green] (2) at (2,0) {};
\vertex [fill=blue] (3) at (1.5,2.5) {};
\vertex [fill=cyan] (4) at (-0.5,1.5) {};
\vertex [fill=purple] (5) at (1,1) {};
\vertex [fill=yellow] (6) at (-1,0) {};
\path[every node/.style={font=\sffamily\small}, line width=0.5pt]
(1) edge (2)
(2) edge (3)
(3) edge (4)
;
```

```

(4) edge (1)
(4) edge (6)
(5) edge (1)
(5) edge (2)
(5) edge (3)
(5) edge (4)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

to get the result

In a similar manner, we can assign colors to the edges also. See the following example:

The code

```

\begin{tikzpicture}
\vertex (u3) at (0,0) [fill]{3};
\vertex (u4) at (2,0) [fill]{4};
\vertex (u5) at (4,0) [fill]{5};
\vertex (u6) at (5,0) [fill]{6};
\vertex (u1) at (1,1) [fill]{2};
\vertex (u2) at (3,1) [fill]{1};
\path
(u1) edge [red,line width= 2.5pt ] (u2)
(u1) edge [red,line width= 2.5pt](u3)
(u1) edge [red,line width= 2.5pt](u4)
(u1) edge (u5)
(u2) edge (u3)
(u2) edge[red,line width= 2.5pt] (u4)
(u2) edge (u5)
(u3) edge[red,line width= 2.5pt] (u4)
(u4) edge (u5)
(u5) edge (u6)
;
\end{tikzpicture}

```

yields the output

References

- [1] J. Cremer, (2011). A very minimal introduction to TikZ, <https://cremeronline.com/LaTeX/minimaltikz.pdf>
- [2] M Hellmund, (2009). PGF/TikZ - Graphics for L^AT_EX, www.math.uni-leipzig.de/~hellmund/LaTeX/pgf-tut.pdf
- [3] A. Mertz, W. Slough (2007). Graphics with TikZ, The PracT_EXJournal, **2007**(1), 22 pages.
- [4] T. Tantau, (2007). Tikz and PGF Manual, Ver-2.10.